

HUMANISM IN INDIAN EDUCATION

(Peer Reviewed)

(Proceedings of the International Seminar)

Chief Editor

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FROM THE DESK OF CHIEF EDITOR

It is a great pleasure on my part to write this note in an unheard of situation. The monstrous virus Covid-19 has shaken the whole world. It has brought uncertainty, fear, social distancing, economic instability, depression and so many crises in our life. In spite of this situation the faculty of Sanskrit department of Chakdaha College has arranged International Webinar. I think it is also a war against this pandemic. This is the time to think about humanity. This is the time to study our Indian literature thoroughly to rejuvenate our self-confidence and will power. This type of academic engagement is important and inevitable for our existence. I am very much thankful to the faculty of Sanskrit Department of my College. With the collective efforts of all staff they are trying to overcome the situation. They are going to publish written document of this webinar. I hope this work would definitely be interesting to the readers and researchers. Congratulations again and best wishes.

Date: 08.08.2020

Place: Chakdaha College

(Swagata Das Mohanta)

Principal
CHAKDAHARA COLLEGE

Prof. (Dr.) Gopalchandra Misra

Formerly Vice-Chancellor, University of Gour Banga
Senior Professor of Sanskrit, Rabindra Bharati University,
West Bengal, India

FOREWORD

I am immensely delighted to learn that a Peer Reviewed journal with ISBN is going to be published by the Principal of Chakdaha College, affiliated to the University of Kalyani. The journal as proposed is supposed to contain the Proceedings of the International Seminar entitled 'Humanism in Indian Education' which was organised by the Department of Sanskrit of the said College on 9/8/2020 to 10/8/2020. The Seminar achieved brilliant success with the august participation of national and international scholars by means of their illuminating contributions.

The endeavour, however, appears to me very laudable and encouraging for the fact that the Editorial Board constituted for the purpose of publication of this volume consists of a galaxy of scholars of different national and international Universities and similar academic Institutions. The volume is going to be edited by Dr. Shiladitya Satpathi with the learned Editorial Board under the patronage of Dr. Swagata Das Mohanta, the revered Principal of Chakdaha College. Again I would like to derive profound pleasure out of the fact that the volume, to my knowledge and belief, shall be very much enriched with multifarious contributions of the scholars and academicians. In this regard too, I like to extend my heartfelt congratulations to the Principal of the College, the learned members of the Advisory Board, the Editor of the volume along with his colleagues for taking such an endeavour to present this kind of significantly academic pursuit to the world of inquisitive readers.

Date: 10. 10. 2020

Place: Kolkata

(Gopalchandra Misra)

Humanistic Approach to Lifelong Learning

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Abstract:

The self-concept developed through humanity inspires people to take lifelong learning. The humanistic approach to lifelong learning is built on the principles of humanity. The present study is conducted to the concept of humanism and principles of humanitarian, importance of humanistic perspective in building lifelong learning, the implications of humanistic education for teachers and policy makers in lifelong learning development, analysis of whether the humanistic approach can be called a learner-centered approach and the challenges of humanistic approach in the path of lifelong learning. The methodology of the study is based on qualitative research method. Data has collected on the basis of secondary sources only. Content analysis has also done of this study. It is found that empathy is never created without humanity and empathy can come only through education which widens the path of lifelong learning and the seeds of liberal mentality gradually begin to appear in the persons. It can be stated in the conclusion of this study education liberates the mind of the people from the darkness of ignorance, illuminates the light of knowledge and evokes a sense of humanity through which the people as well as learners are motivated to receive lifelong learning. So, the path to lifelong learning through humanistic approach becomes much smoother. Universal humanity is needed to reach the specific goal of education as a lifelong learner. Self-realisation is manifested through the lifelong learning of individuals as the astringent of humanity.

Keywords: Education, humanism, humanistic approach, lifelong learning, self-realisation, specific goal.

Introduction:

As a philosophical and ethical position, humanism emphasises the value and centrality of human beings in worldly affairs individually or collectively, and usually focuses on logical thinking and correction rather than established belief system. Although humanistic elements have reflected through education in the ancient times, educational humanism came into its own only after World War II (DeCavalho, 1991). Described as one of the most important process, lifelong learning involves learners' learning in a variety of contexts. The humanistic approach to learning support positive emotions (motivation, empathy, and self-esteem) among learners by avoiding negative emotions (anger, anxiety, stress, and depression) (Palmer, 1997, as cited in Zucca-Scott, 2010). The humanistic approach has a close connection with the learner-centered concept of constructivism. A humanistic approach that incorporates elements of lifelong learning and maintains social dynamism through a lifelong humanitarian perspective develops a liberal mindset and human val-

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ues within the individuals (Kaplan, 2016). The present paper is an attempt to explore the significance of humanistic approach through the concept, principles, and importance of humanism, implications of humanistic education for teachers and policy makers, analyse the reasons for calling the humanistic approach as a learner-centered approach, and the challenges of humanistic approach in the way of lifelong learning. The importance and dignity of human society cannot survive without human values and self-realisation. To meet the objectives of education and specific goal of life, world human society needs to pave the way for a humane approach to lifelong learning.

Historical Background:

The term 'humanismus' is first coined by educational commissioner Fredrich Immanuel Niethammer in 1808 to describe the proposed new classical curriculum in German secondary schools and the word 'humanism' in this sense incorporated into the English language by the year 1836 (Thakur, 2014). The term humanism gained universal acceptance in 1856, when the German historian Georges Voigt is described the Renaissance humanism. In the context of the Italian Renaissance, renaissance movement prospered, stabilised, and existed only to revive classical education (Thakur, 2014). "Historically, humanism found in the writings of Chinese philosopher Confucius (551-471 BC) and the Greek philosopher Epicurus (342-271 BC), reflected justice, rationality, and faith in the human beings, who, not believing in God, wrote of the search for a contented human life, French Enlightenment philosopher Voltaire (1694-1778) often took a stand against enormity and stood for the rights and ethics of free speech, retaining little religious belief. Among the many other writers considered as humanist are David Hume (1711-1776), Jeremy Bentham (1748-1832), Jean Jacque Rousseau (1712-1778), and Bertrand Russell (1872-1970)" (Sharp, 2012, p. 1469). While humanism is not always a description of a particular world view, it is a prescription of how people should behave (Kurtz, 1973).

Review of related Literature:

Edwards (1989) stated that humanism is a school of thought, that believes human beings are different from other species, those abilities have not found in animals. Broome (2014, as cited in Javadi & Tahmasbi, 2020) revealed that in the 1960s and 1970s, many parts of the technical training of humanistic educational programmes were clearly shown in the lengths of innovative self-imagination. Prabhavathy and Mahalakshmi (2016) expressed that one of the 'humanistic' characteristic learning methods is to assume the basic responsibility of the 'whole person' in the learning process. Firdaus and Mariyat (2017) found that education has a significant and strategic role with objectives of education for achieving the importance of a good personality building skills and improving the cognitive intelligence, psychomotor, and affective domain. Shih (2018) explored that a few years ago there was a considerable lack of appropriate environment, favourable situation, and rationalist thinking in the expansion of humanistic education for the alarming reality in several classrooms.

Frias (2019) stated through the humanistic approach, learners drive their own autonomy towards preferences, inspiration, determination, and individual purposes.

Objectives of the Study:

The following objectives have adopted for the study:

- O₁. To study the concept of humanism, principles of humanitarian, and the importance of lifelong learning in humanistic perspective.
- O₂. To highlight the implications of humanistic education for teachers and policy makers in lifelong learning development, humanistic approach as a learner-centered approach, and the challenges of humanistic approach in the path of lifelong learning.

Research Questions:

On the basis of above objectives, the researcher has formulated following research questions:

- RQ₁. What is the concept of humanism?
- RQ₂. What are the principles of humanitarian?
- RQ₃. What is the importance of lifelong learning in humanistic perspective?
- RQ₄. What are the implications of humanistic education for teachers and policy makers in lifelong learning development?
- RQ₅. Why the humanistic approach is called a learner-centered approach?
- RQ₆. What are the challenges of humanistic approach in the path of lifelong learning?

Methodology of Study:

The researcher has taken into consideration the qualitative aspects of the study. This study is purely theoretical based and completely based on secondary data. Content analysis has also done on the available documents. Secondary sources of data has used are selected books (including edited book), journals (including e-journals), and scholarly articles which are written by the great authors.

Objectives-wies Analysis:

The objectives-wise analysis has done with the help of the content analysis method, which is described below:

Analysis of O₁

RQ₁. What is the Concept of Humanism?

The word 'humanism' is derived from the Latin word 'humanus' which means 'human being'. It means a system of thought that deals with human affairs in general (Rao, 2017). Humanism is an ideology that revolves around certain ideas of human nature. Humanism is one of the philosophy of life that goes back centuries. According to this philosophy, people will able to make their own meaning in life without the need of religion, at the same time it emphasises on the scientific methods and critical thinking, for example, humanistic Enlightenment has placed at the centre of psyche (Brink, 2015). Humanism as a pedagogical approach that believes learning is seen as a personal activities to fulfil one's potential

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(Humanism, n.d.). Humanism acknowledges the need for open examination, analysis, remedies, and provides protection from such issues by releasing significance.

The purification of human soul takes place through humanity and self-realisation is awakened in the people, but it certainly requires sympathy, compassion, empathy, and the development of the individuality and mental entity within human beings.

RQ₂. What are the Principles of Humanitarian?

Lifelong learning and development in the humanitarian is based on an integrated approach to knowledge. There are four basic principles in humanitarian i.e. humanity, neutrality, impartiality, and independence. These principles are formally established in 1991 (humanity, neutrality, and impartiality) and 2004 (independence), reiterated by the UN General Assembly (United Nations, 2015, as cited in Rysaback-Smith, 2015) and by the ICRC (ICRC, 2015, as cited in Rysaback-Smith, 2015). Humanity refers to the protection and respect of all human beings and the assistance of all present where necessary. Neutrality is the responsibility of a particular political, religious or any aid organisation not to choose the place of conflict or to support the ideological bent. Impartiality mainly demands support on the basis of differences, including gender, race, nationality or ethnicity, class, political party or religious belief. Finally, independence refers to the autonomy of aid agencies for any political or military purposes (Rysaback-Smith, 2015). Committed to four principles, the UN Code of Conduct, signed by more than 492 aid agencies, provides a set of conventional standards of organisations involved in commitments (OCHA, n.d.).

Principles of humanism help to guide the people in the right direction. This enables the people to develop a strong mindset about the specific goal and empowers, the individuals to work on their own initiative.

RQ₃. What is the importance of Lifelong Learning in Humanistic Perspective?

The basic condition for acquiring learning skills is the humanistic outlook, which paves the way for lifelong learning. Lifelong learning as a continuous process encourages the learner's knowledge, skills, attitudes, and practice throughout his life and the learner can achieve it through formal, non-formal, and informal settings (Ray, 2018). Lifelong learning through humanistic thinking teaches a child to recognise that learning is not limited to childhood or the classroom, it occurs throughout life, and in a variety of situations and it's a level of education through which people are able to make appropriate decisions in any situation of life. The humanistic approach plays an important role in encouraging people to self-explore as well as settings their aim in life. It is an approach that believes the human relationships and interactions are important in this way motivates the learners towards lifelong learning. It also understands that individuals are able to make choices that are influenced by themselves and others, and that choices carry with them a sense of responsibility. It is being realised that a humanistic approach to lifelong learning can be a good step, which will help to overcome the long-term social chaos (Nath, Kumar, & Behura, 2017).

The humanistic approach to lifelong learning needs to be initiated with the aim of organising learners in the path of education at an early stage (Nath et al., 2017).

The humanistic approach to lifelong learning teach the people to overcome social barriers and to show the way to solve various obstacles along the way, enabling the individuals to determine the value of both the living and non-living elements around them.

Analysis of O₂

RQ₄. What are the Implications of Humanistic Education for Teachers and Policy Makers in Lifelong Learning Development?

The implications of humanistic education are crucial for teachers and all the stake holders. It is an approach where learners are actively and deeply engaged in the learning process. Learners who consciously go through certain cognitive processes such as inferring, analysing, synthesising, and evaluating should be considered as independent thinkers. Teachers as a facilitator should take proper care of the learners so, that they understand and co-operate with others. Some of the important implications are discussed below:

- Concentrate on developing a discourse community where learners can actively participate, such as self-assessment, awareness, and sensitivity to self-realised possibilities, ways to engage in learning, and learning ‘how to learn’.
- The implications of the humanistic education are the growth and motivation of learning in the field of education administration, which includes every individual. The job of policy makers and decision makers is to build the organisational environment and its activities properly hence, those individuals can go to the collectively defined ends of the organisation and achieve that goal (Thakur, 2014).
- The administration should ease unnecessary barriers for teachers and learners and reduce their ability to make the best use of potential by creating mutual trust, value, and a valuable environment for them and everyone needs to be motivated to actively participate in the organisational process, to be responsible, to be dutiful, and to share initiatives (Aloni, 2007).
- In-service training programmes should be arranged for teachers hence, that they can develop sensitivity to facilitate the learning process of learners, understand their motivation, and help create that atmosphere for their better development (Lei, 2007).
- Each learning experience should be considered in the content of developing a sense of proper identity in learners and associating that identity with real future achievements.
- The appropriate teacher education programmes should be induced for interpersonal skills and counselling learning.

Only the teachers with their advanced reasoning, thinking, ideals, and well education can guide learners on the path of humanism through lifelong learning. To

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achieve the goal, policy makers need to formulate well thought and ethical policies. It is through this concerted effort of teachers and policymakers that learners are able to reach their specific goal while leading a healthy normal life.

RQ₅. Why the Humanistic Approach is called a Learner-Centered Approach?

Nowadays, the humanistic approach has become a learner-centered approach, in this case, teachers will only help learners to reach the specific goal, also indicate the path to lifelong learning of the learners. Humanistic methods and concepts have restored through learner-centered approach and have re-emerged in mass education as teachers, independence, individual development, and sound evaluation as a learning guide based on learners' interest, significance, and investigation (Hursen, 2011, as cited in Kaplan, 2016). Learner-centered approach and instructions may be helpful in improving learners of motivation, inspiration, interest, curiosity, and learning such as the balance of power, and interaction between teachers and learners, the voice of the learners in educational materials, the role of trainers, learning abilities, responsibilities, and evaluation methods are included (Weimer, 2002). If there is no humanism in nature, the learners couldn't be familiar with the policies of humanity and the humanitarian model teaches learners to solve the problems, and to be motivated to solve the possible issues. Although some European countries are committed to learner-centered approach, they were often weak in support of the policies (Cedefop, 2015). However, instead of the traditional teacher-centric approach, this learner-centered step has taken to increase learners' enthusiasm, interesting, knowledge-seeking, and self-reliance towards education thus, that learners are able to acquire the mentality of lifelong learning by flexible applying the humanistic approach.

In the present pedagogical approach, learners play primary role and teachers play secondary role. In this case, the teachers only show the learners the right path and following the path shown by them the learners are able to acquire self-realisation through humanity.

RQ₆. What are the Challenges of Humanistic Approach in the Path of Lifelong Learning?

Achieving the specific goal of lifelong learning through a humanistic approach faces several number of challenges, these are mentioned below:

- ❖ Some parents, in contrast to secular humanism and misleading educational humanism, opposed religion, and led to the decline of morality, which led them to deviate from the view of humanism (Patterson, 1987).
- ❖ Humanistic instructors have never able to explain humanitarian principles in clear, concise, simple language, and because of their constant ambiguity, everyone has amazed at how the humanistic approach will be applied in the classroom and become the norm for lifelong learning (Conklin, 1984; Patterson, 1987; Willers, 1975).
- ❖ The idea of making learners responsible for self-learning through a humanistic approach has posed a serious challenge to educators in terms of their responsibility to

learners, having a question mark for learners in lifelong learning (Conklin, 1984).

- ❖ As a result of the concentration of cognitive and academic development of standards-based movement from a humanistic approach, affective methods often face adversity on the way to achieving academic purpose (Patterson, 1987).
- ❖ As an outcome of the present emphasis on strong individualism by humanistic approach, many obstacles to lifelong learning i.e. led to selfish behaviour, hedonism, lack of initiative on social issues, humiliation, social stigma, deprivation, frustration etc. (Brockett & Hiemstra, 1991).
- ❖ Focusing on the individual means that if each learner is treated individually, the need for this individual approach may result in a completely fragmented humanistic approach.

But if changing the attitude and behaviour of instructors is part of pre-service teachers training, all of these hindrances to lifelong learning can be overcome through a humanistic approach (Patterson, 1987). Furthermore, if the name of the standards-based movement is changed (Patterson suggested invitational education) and less concern is expressed among the stakeholders, an unimaginable opportunity may come to influence humanity.

Findings of the study:

The major findings are discussed below:

- RQ₁ has revealed that finding the true meaning of life through humanity is the main religion for individuals' learning is a special aspect of individuals' activity, which is also important in the case of evaluation.
- RQ₂ has explored that humanity, neutrality, impartiality, and independence i.e. these four principles of humanitarian guide the learners towards lifelong learning and lead the way in making them right decisions.
- RQ₃ has found that concept of lifelong learning is broad, it can never be confined to a specific boundary, the individuals are able to reach their specific goal through a procurement of different life experiences and as learners become aware of their duties, and they acquire the mentality of overcoming social chaos.
- Furthermore, RQ₄ has found that teachers and policy makers can motivate the learners to pursue lifelong learning. As a bearer of the humanistic approach, teachers as a facilitator will inspire curiosity in the learners, and help them to develop a better mindset. However, the teachers must become a good character, conscientious, and ideal person to the learners.
- RQ₅ has found that present teachers have become the friend, philosopher, and guide of the learners and play a role as facilitator without imposing their own opinions on them. Through this learner-centered approach, learners will become earnest, interested, curious, and passionate, which will pave the way for them to acquire a sense

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of humanity as well as a lifelong learning path.

- RQ₆ has found that practical side of humanism remained complicated due to the errors in interpretation. On the other hand, academics have to face challenges in terms of learners' sense of responsibility and they also observe considerable adversity in achieving academic purpose due to the emphasis on standards-based movement and strong individualism.

Implications of the Society:

Humanism believes that self-realisation and creative ability are vital factors for learners' behaviour. Through human psychology, teachers are able to be humanistic through their approach and it helps to develop creative skills in learners through a flexible and conductive humane environment (Nath et al., 2017). It is very beneficial for both societal health and the environment. Lifelong learning through humanism enhances social prudence of individuals as well as learners and raises awareness about the importance and capability of different elements of the environment.

Concluding Remarks

The study concludes that in order to acquire lifelong learning through a humanistic approach, learners need to possess all these qualities of rationalistic, and critical thinking, equitably, realistic, righteousness, pragmatic learning, and well personality. With all these attributes and features, learners will be able to build a society free from prejudice. Lifelong learning through humanistic approach which emphasises humanism as the most significant element in the learning process. It is with these thoughts that use of the humanistic approach begins, which creates an educational experiences in the present society, where the focus is shifted from achieving academic intention to self-realisation (Javadi & Tahmasbi, 2020). Proving a foundation for individual growth and development is one of the sake of the humanistic approach therefore, that lifelong learning can continue in self-directed manner (Nath et al., 2017, as cited in Javadi & Tahmasbi, 2020). The humanistic approach is regarded as an effective way to ensure lifelong learning of learners and to facilitate the overall development of their personality.

However, the positive and rational attitude of the instructors and stakeholders, parental care towards the children, personality of the teachers, and learners have a special impact on the humanistic approach towards lifelong learning, and also help the learners to become self-reliant and independent.

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